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Features of stress-strain state investigation of “bone – fixator-plate” system when taking into account the mechanical properties orthotropy of cortical bone tissue

Introduction. Osteosynthesis is one of the most efficient methods of bone fractures treatment [1]. Development of modern computer technology and specialized software gives a possibility to perform preliminary estimation of osteosynthesis efficiency. In most papers related to the study of a stress-strain state of “bone-fixator” systems, bone tissue is considered as a homogeneous, isotropic, elastic medium [2]. However, in reality it is heterogeneous and has an anisotropy of mechanical characteristics [3]. This fact indicates that in a case of using a simplified isotropic model of bone tissue, when performing calculations, there is a possibility of obtaining inaccurate results.

The aim of study. To estimate an influence of mechanical properties orthotropy of cortical bone tissue on a stress-strain state of “bone-fixator” system.

Methods. Osteosynthesis of low fracture of fibula is selected. Two simplified numerical models are constructed to solve the problem. These models are different only in properties of cortical bone tissue.

Results. Analysis of a stress state in models elements indicated that normal stresses reached the highest values, and tangential stresses are relatively small. Stress state patterns are qualitatively similar for both computational models. The maximum stresses are the result of their concentration.

Conclusion. Consideration of elastic parameters orthotropy of a bone tissue led to significant quantitative changes in the indicators of a stress state. It is established that the minimum safety margins for both osteosynthesis models turned out to be considered by the maximum tensile stresses acting in the vertical direction. Calculations results indicate a possibility of using an isotropic model of cortical tissue in order to identify the most efficient fixation plate designs.

References:

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